

Heterocycles with Bridgehead Nitrogen : Synthesis, High Resolution NMR and Mass Spectra of 5-Aryloxymethyltetrazolo[1,5-*a*]quinolines

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Tetrazolo[1,5-*a*]quinolines have been found to be phytopathogenic agent against a variety of bacteria and fungi¹. Tetrazolylalkoxycarbostyrils and tetrazolyltetrazolo[1,5-*a*]quinolines have been patented for their vasodilating² and antiallergic³ properties. Further, these compounds have been of spectroscopic interest in view of the solvent and anisotropic effect of the nitrogen lone-pair on the aromatic protons⁴. In continuation of our work on carbostyrils⁵ and 4-aryloxymethylcarbostyrils⁶, the present investigation reports the synthesis of the title compounds in a three-step sequence (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

4-Bromomethylcarbostyril⁷ (1) was reacted with phenols (R = H and CH₃) in presence of alcoholic KOH to obtain the corresponding 4-aryloxymethylcarbostyrils⁶ (2). These were converted to 2-chloro-4-aryloxymethylquinolines (3) by reacting 2 with POCl₃ which upon treatment with sodium azide in ethanol underwent a 1,3-dipolar addition reaction resulting in the tetrazoles (4).

In the pmr spectra, all the four protons of the quinoline ring appeared as ABCD pattern whereas the 4-aromatic protons of the *p*-toloxy moiety (R = CH₃) exhibited the A'A'B'B' pattern. The low-field doublet at δ 8.6 in 4 was assigned to H-9 which is consistent with the earlier observation⁴. The chemical shift of C-3 proton in compound 2 was found to be sensitive to the group located at C-2 and shifted to down-field in compounds 3 and 4. The CH₂O

and CH₃ protons resonated at expected fields (Table 1).

Proton	TABLE 1-PMR SPECTRAL DATA (δ) [R = CH ₃]		
	2 (DMSO-d ₆)	3 (DMSO-d ₆)	4 (CDCl ₃)
H ₃	6.61, s	7.66, s	—
H ₄	—	—	7.26, s
H ₅	7.31 (d, <i>J</i> 8.2 Hz)	8.0 (d, <i>J</i> 8.3 Hz)	—
H ₆	7.21 (t, <i>J</i> 7.7 Hz)	7.72 (t, <i>J</i> 7.2 Hz)	7.91 (d, <i>J</i> 7.4 Hz)
H ₇	7.53 (t, <i>J</i> 7.6 Hz)	7.87 (t, <i>J</i> 7.1 Hz)	7.77 (t, <i>J</i> 7.4 Hz)
H ₈	7.78 (d, <i>J</i> 8 Hz)	8.82 (d, <i>J</i> 8.2 Hz)	8.08 (t, <i>J</i> 5.8 Hz)
H ₉	—	—	8.78 (d, <i>J</i> 8.2 Hz)
NH	11.7 (1H, br)	—	—
CH ₃	2.23 (3H, s)	2.25	2.32
CH ₂	5.36 (2H, s)	5.64 (2H, s)	5.50
H-1',4'	6.99 (<i>J</i> 12 Hz)	7.05 (<i>J</i> 8.5 Hz)	6.95 (<i>J</i> 8.5 Hz)
H-2',3'	8.30 (<i>J</i> 8.2 Hz)	7.13 (<i>J</i> 8.4 Hz)	7.14 (<i>J</i> 8.3 Hz)

The mass spectrum of 4 (R = CH₃) exhibited a low intensity molecular ion peak (I) at *m/z* 290 which underwent a homolytic cleavage of the C–O bond resulting in the loss of *p*-toloxy moiety. The EE ion (II) can eliminate N₂ which is characteristic of tetrazoles and the resulting 3-indolylmethyl cation (V) underwent ring expansion⁸ to eliminate HCN to give the base peak (VI) at *m/z* (128) the further fragmentation of which is established⁹ (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

Experimental

All m.ps. were recorded in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Pmr spectra were recorded on a 270 MHz spectrometer at S.I.F., I.I.Sc., Bangalore. Mass spectrum (EI) was recorded at 70 eV on a Mat CH7 instrument. Satisfactory elemental analyses were obtained for all the compounds.

4-Aryloxymethylcarbostyrils (2a, R = H; 2b, R = CH₃) were prepared according to our reported method⁶.

2-Chloro-4-(aryloxymethyl)quinolines (3) : To compound 2 (0.02 mol) excess of phosphorus oxychloride (0.03 mol) was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed on an oil-bath at 130–40° for 2 h. Excess of POCl₃ was then removed by distillation under reduced pressure. The oily reaction mixture was poured on crushed ice. The separated solid was washed with water and crystallised from benzene : 3a (60%), m.p. 103°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 600 (C=N), 1 245, 1 160 cm⁻¹ (C–O–N); 3b (65%), 99°, ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 610 (C=N), 1 250, 1 180 cm⁻¹ (C–O–C).

5-Aryloxymethyltetrazolo[1,5-a]quinolines (4) : To a suspension of sodium azide (0.02 mol) in a few drops of water, 3 (0.02 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 4–5 h. The solid which separated on cooling was crystallised from acetic acid : 4a (60%), m.p. 181°, ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 335, 1 270 cm⁻¹ (cyclic N=N=N); δ (CDCl₃) 5.3 (2H, s, CH₂–O), 6.7–7.8 (9H, m, ArH) and 8.4 (1H, d, 9-H); 4b (60%), 206°, ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 338, 1 260 cm⁻¹ (cyclic N=N=N); pmr data in Table 1.

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